

Camouflage patterning modulates neural signatures of attention and decision-making

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Supplementary 1: Resources Table

REAGENT OR RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Deposited data		
Raw Data	(20)	doi:10.5061/dryad.wwpzgmsqm
Publication data and R model analysis	(20)	doi:10.5061/dryad.wwpzgmsqm
Software and algorithms		
MATLAB	(1)	https://uk.mathworks.com/
Psychtoolbox	(2)	http://psychtoolbox.org/
EEGLab 2019_1	(3)	https://eeglab.org/
FieldTrip 20200310	(4)	https://www.fieldtriptoolbox.org/
FASTER toolbox 1.2.3b	(5)	https://sourceforge.net/projects/faster/
RStudio 2023-03-0+386	(6)	https://www.r-project.org/
LmerTest R package	(7)	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/lmerTest/
Nnet R package	(8)	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/nnet/
Causal Mediation Analysis R package	(9)	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mediation/
HMAX source code	(10, 11)	https://maxlab.neuro.georgetown.edu/hmax.html
EdgeDis software demo	(22)	https://github.com/Jacsbill/EdgeDis_calc_demo
EEG experiment display code	(21)	https://doi.org/10.5518/1354
EEG preprocessing pipeline and preprocessing data	(21)	https://doi.org/10.5518/1354

Supplementary 2: Calculating Edge Disruption

Edge disruption (EdgeDis) calculations were determined using Riesenhuber and Poggio's (12) hierarchical model of object recognition "HMAX" source code (10, 11) adapted for the purpose of this study. The HMAX (Hierarchical Model and X) model mimics the architecture of the visual cortex, progressing from the early recording of simple cell responses in V1 to the processing of more complex stimulus properties in the inferior temporal lobe.

In the early stages of object recognition, simple cells (S1) respond to orientation properties in the visual scene, such as bars, edges, or gratings, with each cell being selective in its response to a preferred orientation, position, and phase. In contrast, complex cells, whilst being orientation-specific, demonstrate some flexibility regarding the precise positioning of the stimulus within their fields. Moreover, complex cells remain unaffected by phase reversal and will respond consistently to a white bar on a black background or vice versa. Further, the receptive field (region of space in the visual world the cell responds to) gets larger as information moves from C1 to S1.

We calculated the EdgeDis (22) for each stimulus using the S1 and C1 outputs from the HMAX model (10, 11). For both the camouflage and binary cues, we employed six S1 Gabor filter orientations [-30°, -60°, -90°, 0°, 90°, 60°] and nine scale bands [1:17 in steps of 2] for S1. Additionally, we used eight spatial pooling ranges [8:22 in steps of 2] for C1. EdgeDis values for the image were then computed using C1 outputs at a pooling range value of 8, figure S2A shows the dominant orientation identified across the image presented in Figure 1B in the main article.

In creating the EdgeDis score, we identified the parallel orientation (real edges of the cue) by using a location matched binary image (white triangle on black background). This was used to identify the orientation with the maximum unit activations (UA) value (see figure S2B). In each camouflaged cue, we then determined a ratio of UA for the perpendicular (UA_{orth}) and orthogonal (UA_{orth}) orientations. As such, local UA values were calculated as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{UA_{orth_i}}{UA_{orth_i} + UA_{para_i}}$$

A single score for each cue was calculated using the mean of local EdgeDis (exampled in Figure S2C) values in the cue edge region. Thus, higher EdgeDis values represented more edge disruption and, theoretically, more camouflage potential.

A. Cue edge orientations

B. Real edge orientations

C. Local EdgeDis

Figure S2: A. This represents the orientations with the highest unit activation for the image shown in Figure 1B in the main document. B. This illustrates the orientations detected as being parallel with the real cue edges. These were generated using a white triangle on a black background. C. This represents the local EdgeDis values, created by applying formula 1, but before summation.

Supplementary 3: Stimulus Creation and testing detail

All photo/ image modifications and stimulus creation were carried out in Matlab 2019b (1). A photograph of an English oak (*Quercus robur*) tree bark was taken on a GoPro 8 and cropped to 3921*3168 pixels before being converted to grayscale. All background patches were extracted from the same image at random locations. The same image was used for all stimuli to avoid large differences in bark texture or luminance, which could draw attention instead of our intended manipulations.

Cues were created by selecting triangular sections of the bark and placing them in another location on the image, while keeping the rotation of the bark texture either the same or rotated. To create each unique cue stimulus: a) the grayscale tree bark image was randomly rotated from a selection of angles (0, 45, 90°); b) a point [x, y] was randomly selected within the rotated image (with a buffer zone to account for triangle size) to be the 90° vertex of a right-angled triangle with a base size of 128 pixels. The vertex could point up or down (50:50 chance, randomly selected); c) a second random [x, y] point was selected on the 0° rotated tree bark image, and the triangle was placed on the bark in that location; d) a binary texture was imposed on the triangle based on the 25th and 75th percentile points of the original image's grayscale values; e) considering the centre of the triangle as the middle point, the image was further cropped to provide a final 760*651 pixel image for display. For non-cue distractor stimulus rectangles, procedures c) and e) were conducted to create a randomly selected section of the original grayscale bark, also 760*651 pixels.

When creating the four-patch cue screen in Figure 1A (containing four bark patches, only one of which has a triangle), a matching procedure was used to control for factors that could influence attention other than camouflage metrics. A total of 400 cue and 800 non-cue stimuli were created initially and, for each trial, 4 were chosen without replacement (3 non-cue and 1 cue) that were best matched for overall luminance and central region luminance (corresponding to the cue region). This procedure was used to create 348 unique four-patch cue screen stimuli.

TexRot was included as a manipulation to explicitly add some variation in the background matching of the stimulus. With our naturalistic textures, there would be inherent variation in how background matched a stimulus was depending on where it was sampled from, and placed in, the image (i.e., whilst the texture was always the same, dominant orientations and spatial frequencies varied across the naturalistic image). It would be difficult to quantify this variation. As it is known that texture matching influences camouflage potential (13), we included TexRot as a quantifiable metric we could include in the statistical model. It is important to note that whilst linear regression analysis found that EdgeDis differed across TexRot groupings ($b = 0.007$, $se < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$), the differences between groups were of the nature $\text{TexRot } 45^\circ < \text{TexRot } 90^\circ < \text{TexRot } 0^\circ$, there is not a linear relationship between EdgeDis and the degree of texture deviation from matched.

Participants were tested in a darkened EEG lab on a 1920*1080 pixel resolution screen. A single score for each cue was calculated using the mean of local EdgeDis values in the cue edge region. Responses were collected using a Ducky One 2 high-performance mechanical keyboard with Cherry MX switches (14) and a 1000 Hz sampling rate. Participants were asked to always keep their hands on the keyboard. They were asked to respond with the right index and middle finger on the left and right arrows (<, >), and keep their ring, middle, and index finger of the left hand on the 1, 2 & 3 number keys. This was to ensure responses could be given as fast as possible and so participants did not 'lose' the keyboard keys in the darkened room. The specific response keys had additional glow-in-the-dark stickers on them, in case a hand adjustment was required. There were four self-paced rest breaks (usually a few minutes each) during the testing session.

Supplementary 4

Model fitting: The statistical analysis of both behavioural data and ERP ROI data was conducted using R packages 'lmerTest' (7) for linear and general linear mixed effects models (LMM, GLMM) and 'nnet' (8) for multinomial logit models (MLM). A GLMM was used to predict RT using the methods described in Lo and Andrews (15).

Our main hypothesised model was:

$$Outcome = \beta_0 + \beta_1(EdgeDis) + \beta_2(TexRot) + \beta_3(EdgeDis \times TexRot) + b_{0j} + e_{ij}$$

Where EdgeDis and TexRot, as stimulus properties, were interacting predictor variables, along with random intercepts for each participant, j. Or:

$$Outcome = \beta_0 + \beta_1(EdgeDis) + \beta_2(TexRot) + \beta_3(EdgeDis \times TexRot) + \beta_4(CueV) + b_{0j} + e_{ij}$$

when cue validity could have influenced the outcome variable (i.e., EEG responses to the target and behavioural outcomes, but not EEG responses to the cue itself).

To determine if we were selecting the best-fitting models, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values were compared to reduced models, which did not contain an interaction term or TexRot, to ensure we were selecting the right model. In all instances, the reduced models either increased the AIC, thus were less predictive, or reduced it by a negligible amount. Thus, we maintained our hypothesized models. For completeness, we also considered the maximal model, as considered good practice by Barr et al. (16). However, the random effect structure was too complicated in these models, resulting in singularity. As we had no reason to believe there would be a random slope for each participant, we continued with our hypothesized models.

Timeseries data: ERP data were averaged across 50 ms windows, with 50 ms increments within the occipital region of interest electrodes. To mitigate the risk of false positives resulting from multiple comparisons inherent in time series analysis, we implemented a cluster level thresholding procedure (ClusterP). Monte Carlo simulations (17) were conducted with 1000 repetitions for each of the 33 increments. These simulations were performed on the time series with randomised independent variable labels. Clusters with a size of two or greater were considered significant at the 95% confidence interval, clusters with a size of three or greater were considered significant at the 99% confidence interval, and clusters with a size of four or greater were considered significant at the 99.99% confidence interval.

Supplementary 5

Figure S5A: Mean and 95% confidence intervals of N2pc (averaged ERP 300-400msec) following the cue (N2pcCue) stimulus for categorised degree of EdgeDis.

Figure S5B: Mean and 95% confidence intervals of the N2pc following the target stimulus (N2pcTarget) for categorised degree of EdgeDis, by cue validity.

Supplementary 6

We note that there was evidence of a raise in the ERP magnitude within the central parietal ROI following the cue (cue locked CPP, see Figure S6) that could have potentially reflected evidence accumulation directly following the camouflage cue.

A CPP timeseries analysis was run from cue onset at 50 ms increments until just prior to target onset, using a cluster-level correction (ClusterP) technique to correct for multiple comparisons. An early significant period (500-750 ms) was evident in which both certainty and accuracy significantly predicted CPP amplitude (certainty: $F(2, 57533) = 3.396$, $p < 0.05$, ClusterP: $p < 0.000$; accuracy: $F(1, 5761) = 6.330$, $p < 0.05$, ClusterP: $p < 0.000$; interaction: $F(1, 5755) = 1.425$, $p = 0.241$, Figure S6A and S6B). Estimates for both certainty (fairly sure: $b = 0.062$, $se = 0.049$, CI [0.017 – 0.141], certain: $b = 0.112$, $se = 0.045$, CI [0.017 – 0.141]) and accuracy ($b = -0.033$, $se = 0.053$, CI [-0.137 – 0.071]) determine that this early rise in the central parietal was of greater amplitude as both accuracy and certainty increased.

A later CPP (1150-1300 ms) was also significantly predicted from behavioural responses, but this time by certainty only (certainty: $F(2, 5761) = 5.663$, $p < 0.01$. ClusterP: $p < 0.01$; accuracy: $F(1, 5754) = 3.734$, $p = 0.053$; interaction: $F(2, 5751) = 2.591$, $p = 0.075$). Certainty estimates (fairly sure: $b = -0.139$, $se = 0.047$, CI [-0.034 – 0.158]; certain: $b = -0.137$, $se = 0.047$, CI [0.024 – 0.199]) were larger but also in the opposite direction. We can see that this period corresponded with a sustained central parietal peak for guess trials, while the central parietal ERP for fairly sure and certain trials has begun to decline. However, it was evident from the topography of the cue locked central parietal development that it was not typical of those seen in evidence accumulation tasks (18, 19). The signature is largely influenced by early occipital positivity, along with a right dorsolateral peak and is not a classic CPP associated with decision-making tasks. This is likely because the cue on its own did not require a decision, but rather the decision was delayed until after the target.

Figure S6: Cue locked central ERP, including: A. Topographical plots at three time points and B. ongoing ERP signature.

B. Central parietal ERP by certainty (cue locked)

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